

THE MOLECULAR POLARISATIONS AND APPARENT DIPOLE MOMENTS OF TITANIUM TETRACHLORIDE, TIN TETRACHLORIDE AND TIN TETRAIODIDE IN NON-POLAR SOLVENTS

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Titanium tetrachloride and tin tetraiodide are found to be non-polar, whereas tin tetrachloride is found to be polar, irrespective of the solvent used. The former two halides apparently possess tetrahedral structures with the metal atom at the centre of the grouping, whereas tin tetrachloride has pyramidal structure with tin at the apex. The total polarisation of each of the three halides at infinite dilution, whether obtained from Debye's or modified equations, varies with the solvent, thus indicating inadequacy of those equations based on modified field theory to account for the effect of the solvent. The ratio of the polarisation at infinite dilution calculated from any modified equation to that calculated from Debye's equation is invariable with the solvent and appears to be higher for a polar than for a non-polar halide. From such calculations it seems likely that substances of near apparent dipole moment values should possess nearly the same ratio.

Tetravalent metal halides are attracting now the attention of many investigators due to their use as starting materials for the production of these metals. It is therefore of theoretical and practical interest to obtain information regarding the structure of these halides. In spite of its importance as an effective tool in elucidating molecular structures, the method of dipole moment has only been scarcely applied to these metal halides, and the results obtained are either varying or fortuitous where agreement has been attained. Tin tetrachloride, for example, was found by Ulich and co-workers (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **B17**, 369) to be polar in benzene and non-polar in carbon tetrachloride, whereas Bergmann *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1931, **B13**, 232), who carried out measurements only in carbon tetrachloride, found it to be polar. Although the experimental procedure of the latter authors was criticised by the former ones, they both arrived at the same conclusion in respect of the structure of titanium tetrachloride when using the solvent carbon tetrachloride. These authors applied in their calculations Debye's equation which was then modified by others (Henriquez, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1935, **54**, 574; Newton, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 1937, **224**, 583; *Trans Faraday Soc.*, 1951, **47**, 1304; Kirkwood, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 911) to account for the mutual interaction between molecular dipoles.

The object of the present investigation is to determine the dipole moments of the tetravalent halides: titanium and tin tetrachlorides and tin tetraiodide, by carrying out dielectric constant measurements in non-polar solvents as benzene and carbon tetrachloride, and to examine the feasibility of the assumption of the non-solvent effect, by using the modified equations.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Chemically pure titanium and tin tetrachlorides were subjected four times to vacuum distillation, following a method similar to that given by Archibald ("The Preparation of Pure Inorganic Substances", New York, 1932, pp. 184, 212). Tin tetraiodide was crystallised thrice from CCl_4 , well dried and then subjected to the same treatment as the chlorides. Benzene, CCl_4 and nitrobenzene of "Analar" grade were rigorously dried and purified according to recommended procedures (Weissberger and Proskauer, "Organic Solvents, Physical Constants and Methods of Purification", 1935, pp. 105, 107, 163).

Measurements.—The dielectric constant, ϵ , was measured using a resonance circuit in which a frequency of 10^8 cycles per second was fixed by a quartz crystal. The silvered Sayce-Briscoe measuring cell (Le Fèvre, "Dipole Moments", Methuen, 1948, p. 32) could not be applied on account of chemical interaction with the halides, and thus, a specially designed cylindrical platinum cell was used. It was rigidly fixed in a jacket that could be connected to an ultra-thermostat. The air-capacity of the cell was $30\mu\text{F}$, the range over which ϵ could be measured was 1.9–3.1 and the volume required to fill the annulus was 8 c.c. In the calibration of the apparatus, only liquids of reliable dielectric constants were used, thus:

ϵ at 25°	...	Benzene*†	* CCl_4	**Nitrobenzene in benzene.		
		2.2725	2.2270	2.2925	2.3000	2.3325
				$f_2=0.0008707$	0.001197	0.002612

*Le Fèvre, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, 34, 1129.

†Hartshorn *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, 123A, 664.

** Le Fèvre *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1936, 49, 1136; Jenkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 482.

The uncertainty in ϵ was ± 0.0005 .

The density was measured by a pycnometer of the Sprengel-Ostwald type that was filled by the method of Smyth and Morgan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 1547) and Miller (*ibid.*, 1934, 56, 2360). The refractive index for the Na_D line was directly measured by means of a Hilger-Abbe refractometer. The concentration was determined, using Dorfman and Hildebrand's method (*ibid.*, 1927, 49, 729). All measurements were made at $25^\circ \pm 0.002^\circ$.

The total molecular polarisation of the halide, P_2 , at different concentrations was calculated using the modified Clausius-Mosotti-Debye equation (Le Fèvre, "Dipole Moments", 1948, p. 7; Debye, "Handbuck. der Radiologie", 1925, pp. 6, 600) applicable to solutions. The polarisation at infinite dilution, $P_{2\infty}$, was graphically and mathematically determined. In the latter case, the Hedestrand method (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, B2, 428) and the Palit-Banerjee method (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 1299) were used. The mean of the values of $P_{2\infty}$, as deduced by the three methods, was then taken. The part of the molecular polarisation arising from induced dipoles, R_2 , was calculated from measurements of n_D using the modified form of Lorenz-Lorentz equation (Le Fèvre, "Dipole Moments," pp. 11, 17) applicable to solutions and then

TABLE I

Solvent.	t° .	P_{200} (Debye) (c.c.)	* α .	$\beta^{\dagger}$.	P_2 (c.c.) (X 10 ¹⁸).	$A^{\dagger} P_2$ (c.c.) (X 10 ¹⁸).	μ_R .	P_{200} (modified formulae) (c.c.)		Ref.		
								Graphical. Hedestrand. Hennerjee. value.	Palit & Mean Hennerjee. value.		Henriquez. Kirkwood. Newton.	Present authors
Titanium tetrachloride.												
Benzene	14.7-20.0°	44.45	...	...	37.8	2.70	0	...	...	Ulich <i>et al.</i>		
	25.0°	43.93	44.09	44.10	0.5611	0.9430	37.10	3.71	0	48.32	53.95	68.03
CCl ₄	15.0-18.0°	40.41	...	...	...	37.8	2.70	0	...	...	...	Ulich <i>et al.</i>
	19.8°	43.2	...	...	...	43.23	...	0	...	...	...	Bergmann
	25.0°	40.31	40.34	40.33	0.5591	0.1992	36.86	3.69	0	44.02	49.18	62.07
Tin tetrachloride.												
Benzene	14.7-20.0°	58	...	...	...	35.2	8.10	0.80	...	...	...	Ulich <i>et al.</i>
	25.0°	56.65	56.79	56.64	1.3502	1.7015	34.26	3.43	0.96	63.35	72.24	92.88
CCl ₄	15.0-18.0°	43.45	...	...	...	35.2	8.10	0	...	...	...	Ulich <i>et al.</i>
	17.7°	52.5	...	...	...	...	...	0.80	...	...	...	Bergmann
	25.0°	53.45	53.32	53.42	1.1453	0.7148	38.91	3.44	0.86	59.31	67.26	86.14
Tin tetraiodide.												
Benzene	25.0°	26.70	...	...	...	...	30	0	...	...	...	Williams
	25.0°	26.50	26.84	26.65	0.5967	6.4226	...	2.47	0	29.60	33.67	43.20

* $\alpha = \frac{\Delta \epsilon_{12}}{\Delta f_2}$, where ϵ_{12} is the dielectric constant of the solution and f_2 is the mol. fraction of the solute ($\epsilon_{12} = \epsilon_1 + \alpha f_2$).

† $\beta = \frac{\Delta^2 d_{12}}{\Delta f_2^2}$, where d_{12} is the density of the solution ($d_{12} = d_1 + \beta f_2$).

α and β are determined by the method of least squares.

corrected by means of the dispersion formula,

$$\left(1 - \frac{\lambda_0^2}{\lambda^2}\right) R_2,$$

where $\lambda_0 = 1013 \text{ \AA}$ (Miller, *loc. cit.*) and $\lambda = 5896 \text{ \AA}$ (Allsopp and Willis, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1936, 153A, 379) so as to get the molecular refraction for infinite wave-length, $R_{2\infty}$, which is identical with the electronic polarisation ${}_e P_2$. The deformation polarisation, ${}_d P_2$, was taken as 1.10 $R_{2\infty}$ (Zahn and Miles, *Phys. Rev.*, 1928, 32, 497) and the dipole moment μ was obtained by the refractivity method (Le Fèvre, *loc. cit.*, p. 12).

The modified formulae of Henriquez, Kirkwood and Newton (vide Smith and Witten, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 1315) were also used in evaluating the polarisation at infinite dilution for studying the solvent effect. The results obtained are summarised together with those of previous workers in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Titanium Tetrachloride.—The electronic polarisation value is in better agreement with Ulich's value (*loc. cit.*) than with that of Bergmann (*loc. cit.*). The orientation polarisation is zero in CCl_4 and 3.29 c.c. in benzene. Thus, titanium tetrachloride is a dipole-free halide and may be considered as a tetrahedral grouping around Ti in agreement with previous results arrived at by other different methods (Wierl, *Ann. Physik*, 1931, v, 8, 521; Trumphy, *Z. Physik*, 1930, 66, 790).

TABLE II

$t = 25^\circ$.

Halide.	Solvent	$P_{2\infty}$ (in c.c.)			
		Kirkwood.	Henriquez.	Newton.	Debye.
TiCl_4	C_6H_6	53.95	48.32	68.03	44.10
	CCl_4	49.18	44.02	62.07	40.33
SnCl_4	C_6H_6	72.24	63.35	92.88	56.64
	CCl_4	67.26	59.31	86.14	53.42
SnI_4	C_6H_6	33.67	29.60	43.20	26.65

TABLE III

$t = 25^\circ$.

Halide.	Solvent.	$\frac{P_{2\infty K}}{P_{2\infty D}}$	$\frac{P_{2\infty H}}{P_{2\infty D}}$	$\frac{P_{2\infty N}}{P_{2\infty D}}$	$\mu_D \times 10^{18}$
		TiCl_4	C_6H_6	1.22	
	CCl_4	1.22	1.09	1.54	0
SnCl_4	C_6H_6	1.27	1.11	1.64	0.95
	CCl_4	1.26	1.11	1.61	0.86
SnI_4	C_6H_6	1.27	1.11	1.62	0

Tin Tetrachloride.—The electronic polarisation value is very near to Ulich's value but not appreciably lower than that of Bergmann. The atomic polarisation of this

halide was determined by the former author as the difference between its total polarisation in the solid state and its electronic polarisation; the value obtained being 8.10 c.c. in agreement with 10.8 c.c. obtained by Smyth (*Phil. Mag.*, 1925, 50, 361) by the same method. Jenkins (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 739) considering non-existence of atomic polarisations higher than 7 c.c., ascribed those in the neighbourhood of 10 c.c. to the hygroscopic nature of the halide. If, however, the atomic polarisation value due to Ulich were estimated as 10% of the electronic polarisation, a value of 3.52 c.c. would have been obtained, which is as low as our value of 3.43 c.c., determined by the same method. The dipole moment of this halide, when determined in CCl_4 , is 0.86 D, thus agreeing with Bergmann's value of 0.80 D and deviating from that of Ulich, which is zero. Although the total polarisation, as determined in CCl_4 , is quite comparable with that of Bergmann and higher than that of Ulich, yet it could not be ascribed to the probable presence of water, as was inferred by Ulich when discussing Bergmann's data, firstly because the total polarisation of this halide, when determined in benzene, is found to be very near to that of Ulich, and secondly, because there is no reason to assume that the presence of water would have a detrimental effect greater in CCl_4 than in benzene, since the solubility of HCl in the former solvent is less than that in the latter (Faibrother, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 43).

The assumption therefore, made by Ulich that tin tetrachloride forms in benzene associate complexes giving rise to the observed orientation term and the absence of such tendency in CCl_4 , appears to be unnecessary. This compound may accordingly be conceived to possess a pyramidal structure with Sn located at the apex so as to account for the presence of an electric doublet in the molecule, detectable in the different non-polar solvents.

The higher polarisation values at infinite dilution in benzene than in CCl_4 for the two halides may be attributed to the higher dissociating power of the former solvent (Van Arkel and Snoek, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1933, 52, 719). Also by taking into account the properties of the solute besides those of the solvent, Weigle (*Helv. Phys. Acta*, 1933, 6, 681) concludes that when polarisation measurements of one substance are carried out in different solvents, the solvent with the higher dielectric constant yields greater polarisation value.

Tin Tetraiodide.—Measurements on tin tetraiodide show that this compound is non-polar. This agrees with the previous work carried out by Williams and Allgeier (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 2416) and with the conclusion drawn out by Hildebrand ("Solubility", 1924, Chap. 14; Dorfman and Hildebrand, *loc. cit.*) from solubility determinations in different organic solvents. This halide may therefore be considered, in analogy with titanium tetrachloride, to possess a tetrahedral structure with tin at the centre of grouping.

Application of Modified Formulae.—Kirkwood's equation (*loc. cit.*) has been considered to be the most reliable equation for representing the total molecular polarisation of a polar molecule when the mutual interaction between molecular dipoles is taken into account. The polarisation value given by this equation is thus considered to be the nearest to the true value, *i. e.*, the value which would be obtained by applying Debye's equation to the gaseous state. The molecular polarisation, determined

by Kirkwood's equation, must be higher than that determined by Debye's equation, as in the first case the molecule is considered to be acted upon by two fields of force: the external field and that arising from the surrounding dipoles. Consequently, it becomes easier for the molecule to be oriented, thus leading to an increase in the value of the orientation polarisation. In order to investigate the solvent effect, Kirkwood's as well as Henriquez' and Newton's equations (*loc. cit.*) were applied for calculating $P_{2\infty}$. The values obtained are shown in Table II from which it can be seen that $P_{2\infty}$ for one halide varies with the solvent, thus indicating that even those equations, which are based on a modified theory, do not satisfactorily account for the solvent effect. Similar conclusions were drawn by Smith and Witten (*loc. cit.*) with respect to some organic substances. The effect of the solvent on the ratio between $P_{2\infty}$ obtained from each modified formula and that obtained from Debye's formula, and the dependence of this ratio on the polarity of the substance have been traced. The data shown in Table III reveal that the ratio for one halide is nearly the same in the two different solvents and that the increase in polarity is accompanied with a slight increase in the ratio. This result can be further supported when similar calculations are made on the Smith and Witten data. One can therefore predict that substances of near dipole moment values should be of the same ratio. However, further work is necessary to substantiate this prediction.

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